
ENTREPRENEURIAL INTERNATIONALISATION: BEHAVIOURS AND COMPETENCIES FOR SUCCESSFUL BUSINESS PERFORMANCE

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Abstract

Entrepreneurs over time have sought out ways of improving their business performance through internationalisation. Successful business performance in international markets requires certain behaviours and competencies. Entrepreneurs therefore need to develop these behaviours and competences to succeed. The study aims to investigate the behaviours and competences that enable entrepreneurs to succeed in international markets, through extensive literature review. It was concluded from the research that successful entrepreneurial internationalisation requires specific behaviours and competencies such as risk taking, innovative mindset and resilience. It was also highlighted that the leadership behaviour of entrepreneurs is essential for the achievement of sustainable growth and overcoming complexities which may be evident in international markets. The study contributes theoretically to understanding entrepreneurial internationalisation and highlights the importance of developing certain behaviours and competences which provides insights for entrepreneurs and other stakeholders, offering a roadmap towards improving business performance. The results contribute to stakeholders' awareness to developing policies which will empower entrepreneurs to contribute favourably to the Gross Domestic Product of their countries.

Keywords: Entrepreneurial Internationalisation, Behaviours, Competencies, Business Performance.

1.1 Introduction

Successful business performance for firms includes employee and stakeholder satisfaction, operational efficiency and positive financial results. Kaplan (2009) explained how the balanced scorecards which integrates both financial and non-financial metrics could be used by organisations to assess the health of their organisations. High business performance is crucial for firms to be able to strive and have competitive edge. Firms that are successful and have sustained successful performance over time are innovative, tend to make use of their resources effectively and adapt easily to change (Hoskisson et al., 2011).

According to Magni et al. (2022), Successful internationalisation requires entrepreneurs to develop behaviours and competencies that will help them improve their firm performance. These behaviours include innovation, cultural communication and risk-taking. It is when these behaviours and competencies are prioritised that entrepreneurs can achieve sustainable growth and embrace opportunities available in international markets.

Today's business landscape is very competitive and dynamic, and it therefore requires sustainable performance which could be achieved by adopting the right behaviours and competences. It is important to understand the relationship between these behaviours and competences, how they impact on business performance and how this contributes to the ability of entrepreneurs to overcome business challenges and grow. Small and medium scale enterprises (SMEs) promote export, and they have the entrepreneur as the main decision-maker. An enterprise expanding into international markets is a decision which is driven by strategy and focus of the entrepreneur to improve firm performance (Denicolai et al., 2015). According to Ruzzier M et al. (2006), internationalisation brings about new opportunities for firms to improve on their product delivery thereby increasing their customer base and revenue. McDougall and Oviatt (2000), supports this by stating that Entrepreneurial Internationalisation enables firms to create value for their firms through adapting to certain behaviours and competences. It is important to understand the role the entrepreneur plays in internationalisation by reviewing their behaviours and competences. Internationalisation comes with its challenges, and this has affected entrepreneurs in the continuity of their businesses. These challenges include political and environmental changes in the business landscape which has brought about a reduction in the significant role SMEs play in their contributions to employment, fiscal revenue and economic development (Lawless, 2014). Some studies have been carried out on how entrepreneurs can overcome challenges in internationalisation; However, little study is directed at how behaviours and competences could add to the success story of entrepreneurs. It is particularly important to understand how entrepreneurs behave and develop in challenging environments such as evolving markets with different institutional frameworks interna (Welter & Smallbone, 2011).

Based on the importance of SMES to the growth of economies, this research will therefore be examining the behaviours and competences of entrepreneurs which will enable them to be successful. It will address successful internationalisation and link it to specific behaviours and competencies to give an understanding on the impact behaviours and competencies have on entrepreneurial internationalisation. Key behaviours and competencies that improve business performance will be identified thereby providing valuable insights to stakeholders and entrepreneurs who are interested in improving business performance especially in international markets.

1.2 Statement of the problem

In this era where there is an increase in globalised economies, entrepreneurial internationalisation is a strategy being used by businesses that seek sustainable growth to gain

competitive advantage (Dadzie et al., 2021). There is a growing interest in internationalisation by firms however, cultural differences, constraints in raising capital, and unfamiliar markets hinders some firms from going into international markets. It is therefore necessary for these firms to develop certain behaviour and competencies to be able to successful. As Ringo et al. (2022) stated, SMEs should endeavour to develop their competences such that they will become more profitable. Jardim (2021), stated that the entrepreneurs are depended upon for developing the right competences for successful business performance, noting that in navigating challenges, new ways of thinking and working ought to be embraced by the entrepreneurs.

These behaviours and competencies includes risk management, adaptability and cross-cultural communication (Crovini et al., 2021). McDougall and Oviatt (2000), identified lack of decision-making skills and inadequate management of risks as factors that could affect the ability of entrepreneurs from facing challenges eminent in international markets. They could miss out on seizing the right opportunities, collaborations and partnerships which could have facilitated their market entry and growth, and this will ultimately limit their potential to succeed in international markets. Without being proactive, businesses may not be able to innovate, and this leads to sub-optimal performance, a decline in their share of the market or total stagnation (Gorissen et al., 2016). According to Alkaabi (2022), lack of the right skill makes them unable to navigate global market challenges and this leads to ineffective strategies, misunderstanding of consumer customs and preferences, wrong market approach, poor sales, poor decision making, ineffective communication and low customer engagement. Purnomo et al. (2021), supported this, stating that the lack of right behaviours and competencies are factors affecting survival and growth of entrepreneurs.

All these deficiencies reduce the potential for growth and leads to continuous cycle of performance that is below average especially in an environment where competition keeps increasing. Maintaining and improving on their behaviours and competences has enabled some entrepreneurs to have sustained business success and contribute to the GDPs of their countries. Jayasundara et al. (2020), stressed that entrepreneurs should continue to improve and overcome challenges that has affected their business performance.

This study focuses on the entrepreneur who acts as the key decision maker in SMEs. The study seeks to identify key behaviours and competences essential to improving internationalisation and support entrepreneurs by providing effective strategies to enable them to navigate the complexities evident in global markets.

2.0 Literature Review

2.1 Entrepreneurial Internationalisation

Entrepreneurial internationalisation is a critical aspect for growth of businesses especially due to advancements in technology and globalisation. Oviatt and McDougall (2005) define entrepreneurial internationalisation as a process that involves the movement of firms to foreign environments to identify and exploit opportunities. According to Knight and Cavusgil (2004), this is different from what traditional organisations do because entrepreneurial internationalisation involves a rapid process supported by innovation, strategic thinking and gaining competitive advantage over competition. Internationalisation refers to the process of businesses expanding beyond their domestic border which has increased opportunities for SMEs to go into exportation. Countries always seek out opportunities for a positive trade balance, using exportation as a tool to achieve this (Youshanlouei et al., 2013). Oviatt and McDougall (2005) further explained that entrepreneurial internationalisation is a process of starting a new business and having the intention of going into international markets from inception. Cavusgil and Knight (2015)

explain that entrepreneurial internationalisation is a situation where the firm, from inception will engage in business activities internationally. Expanding on this view, Magni et al. (2022) stated that it involves entry into international markets and developing capabilities that will enable the firm to successfully continue its operations internationally. Rialp et al. (2005), see entrepreneurial internationalisation as a process that is dynamic and involves the firm gradually penetrating international markets. Matusinaite and Sekliuckiene (2015), stated that organisations can discover opportunities internationally through entrepreneurial internationalisation and this will further enable the creation of innovative products and services for customers.

All these definitions show that it is important to have the necessary knowledge and skills to be able to enter different markets, and the process is complex, requiring building capacity, adaptability and proactive engagement from the beginning of the business. There are so many challenges to internationalisation faced by firms, however improving behaviours and competences may enable firms to overcome these challenges (Yener et al., 2014). The strategic combination of behaviours and competences to create added value to products and services is referred to as Entrepreneurial internationalisation (McDougall & Oviatt, 2000).

The study carried out by Stevenson and Jarillo (2016) on entrepreneurship showed that entrepreneurship behaviours can be grouped into categories of the way they act, the reasons why they act the way they do and what results they get after their actions. The results from the study showed the reflection of entrepreneurial actions on successful performance of the business. Slevin & Covin (1997) explained that there are common foundational elements of the behavioural process and thus described internationalisation as a combination of risk-seeking, value-creation, proactivity, behaviour, and innovation. It is therefore important to understand how a combination of behaviours develop competitive advantage to firms.

The importance of entrepreneurial Internationalisation cannot be over emphasised. Entrepreneurial industrialisation is a key contributor to the UN sustainable development goals. It contributes to sustainable economic development as well as job creation and this ultimately reduces poverty (Dhahri et al., 2021). Entrepreneurial internationalisation supports industry through innovative behaviours and provision of new services and products. The activities carried out by entrepreneurs in international markets promotes industrialisation and infrastructural development leading to capacity building and knowledge sharing (Oliinyk et al., 2019). Another aspect of entrepreneurial internationalisation activities that supports the UN sustainability goals is in collaborations undertaken through networking and cross-cultural exchanges. This enables them to build partnerships that foster inclusive economic growth and sustainability. Entrepreneurial Internationalisation therefore does not only bring about improvement in the economy but also supports the broader goals of global collaboration towards a sustainable future.

In conclusion entrepreneurial internationalisation is a dynamic and complex process which is driven by possession of the right behaviours and competencies. As the economy continues to evolve, businesses that thrive to develop these competencies will be able to successfully internationalise and gain competitive advantage over their peers in the industry.

2.2 Theoretical Framework

Theories of entrepreneurial internationalisation show how firms move into international markets. The entrepreneur is seen as the driver of organisations through the adoption of different strategies to internationalisation (Andersson, 2000). According to Crick and Spence (2005), a holistic approach should be used in undertaking research on entrepreneurship as a combination of theories will enable firms to succeed as the theories explain how and why

firms go into international markets. International entrepreneurship theories explain how entrepreneurs identify and exploit opportunities beyond their countries including navigating challenges and complex situations. The personal characteristics, access to resources, cultural and institutional differences, and the competitive environments are all determining factors to successful internationalisation

The Uppsala model

This model suggests that firms internationalise by exporting to countries that are close to theirs by distance, language and culture and gradually move to distant countries when they have developed their learning experimentally. This approach gives the entrepreneur more experience and knowledge through lower modes of commitment such as exports then later go into higher modes of commitments as they understand the market better (Vahlne & Johanson, 2017).

The Network Model

This model propounded by Johanson & Mattsson in 1988, suggests that networks and relationships should be leveraged to facilitate the process of internationalisation. It highlights that good relationships with customers, suppliers and other partners could significantly increase entrepreneurial success in internationalisation (Johanson & Mattsson, 2013).

The Eclectic Paradigm

The idea behind this model is ownership specific advantages which enable firms to avoid market imperfections and make exceptional profits from the situations. These ownership advantages include factors such as trade secrets or exclusive information and access to natural resources or markets. After weighing all transaction costs and other factors, they decide to go into the market (Dunning, 1988). This theory is supported by the Resource-based View theory developed by Barney in, which suggest that the unique capabilities and resources of firms is what aids them to have competitive advantage in international markets. When entrepreneurs possess valuable resources such as skilled personnel, capabilities in technology and intellectual property, they are in a better position to successfully expand internationally (Taher, 2011).

Born-Global Theory

This theory was propounded by Knight and Cavusgil, (2004) and it is about the way firms including SMEs move to international markets. The Born-global firms refer to firms that rapidly internationalise soon after they are set up. It shows the role innovation, operating in niche markets and technology play for firms to easily access markets internationally (Cavusgil & Knight, 2015). It is very similar to the international new ventures' theory by (Oviatt & McDougall, 1994), which focuses on firms that internationalise from inception, with emphasis on operation and formation challenges these firms may encounter in the marketplace (Oviatt & McDougall, 2018).

Innovation-Related Internationalisation Theory

This theory highlights the link between innovation and internationalisation, implying that a firm will succeed internationally if able to innovate and bring out unique products and services to customers. The unique products and services are differentiated from the local competitors, giving them an edge to improve on their business performance (Zahra & George, 2017).

2.3 Entrepreneurial Behaviours and Competences for Success

An essential element in the entrepreneurial process according to Slevin and Covin (1997), is behaviour. This means the actions exhibited is the major makeup of the entrepreneur.

Competency is a combination of behaviours, skills, abilities and personal characteristics of individuals which lead to them performing successfully in their ventures (RezaeiZadeh et al., 2017). Behaviours and competences include leadership behaviour and managerial capabilities, knowledge, networking, risk-taking, innovation and critical thinking (Ngigi et al., 2018). Competencies and behaviours therefore affect people's outcomes and depending on the situations individual's face, it could either improve or reduce their performance.

Behaviours and competences are necessary for the success of small and medium scale enterprises (SMEs), because it aids their ability to effectively compete in the market. There are different challenges which SMEs face, such as raising capital, infrastructural constraints and market access and it therefore requires the right behaviours and competences to navigate these challenges (Baylie & Singh, 2019). SMEs have between 10 to 250 employees, and play a significant role in businesses, contributing to 90% of businesses worldwide, 50% towards employment, and 40% towards the Gross domestic income (GDI) of economies (Umar et al.) The development and support of SMEs should be highly prioritised as it has been estimated that they will contribute an estimated figure of 600 million jobs by 2030 with the expected global workforce growth (Umar et al.)

Research has shown the importance of entrepreneurial behaviours and competencies for successful business performance across different industries. According to Lumpkin and Dess (1996), risk taking, proactiveness, innovativeness and resilience have been linked to firms that have performed well in their businesses while inadequate networking skills, poor management of risks and lack of cultural awareness have been identified as skills that have limited entrepreneurs from navigating effectively into international markets (Cavusgil & Knight, 2015). Avlonitis and Salavou (2007), defined innovativeness as the inclination of a firm to engage in new processes, ideas or products that have been proven to positively support business success in terms of growth in sales or expansion in the business share of the market. Tian et al. (2022), mentioned that entrepreneurs that are proactive will easily identify opportunities that will improve their businesses. The firms will be able to identify new opportunities that will enable them to adapt to market conditions, considering how dynamic the market is. Likewise, they added that vital competencies for international business success include resource management, strategic thinking and cross-cultural communication. These competencies enable the entrepreneurs to allocate resources effectively.

Ismail (2022) defined competencies as those personal attributes, knowledge and skills which help in effective decision making and are critical to success in business performance. On the other hand, cross cultural skills aid entrepreneurs in their internationalisation efforts by making them negotiate with various stakeholders, build trust and easily navigate changes that come up in the market. Zhou and Charoensukmongkol (2022) supported this, mentioning that cross cultural skills and competencies enable entrepreneurs to make more successful partnerships and sales internationally due to their ability to navigate the differences in culture.

Another area is self-efficacy of the entrepreneur which relates closely with strategic decision making and persistence. It has to do with the personal belief of entrepreneur that they will succeed. This behaviour enables them to succeed in the overall business performance of the organisation. It was highlighted that entrepreneurs that have self-efficacy set higher goals and are more persistence which adds up to the successful performance of their businesses. Graham (2022) supported, stating that self-efficacy is a psychological competency that has been identified, which influences individuals to make strategic decisions, and pushes them to be resilient and persistent in facing and navigating challenges.

Brown-Crawford (2022) mentioned that poor leadership skills could also create a workforce that is disengaged, impacting negatively on morale and productivity. The study carried out by Görgens-Ekermans and Roux (2021) emphasized the role which emotional intelligence plays in improving leadership skills, thereby enabling the leader to successfully lead teams. Emotional intelligence equips the entrepreneurs to create a positive work environment through ability to effectively motivate their teams and resolve conflicts in the workplace.

The above studies collectively show that successful entrepreneurial internationalisation involves a combination of distinctive behaviours and competencies which influences entrepreneurial success, making them able to adapt, innovate and effectively compete and this ultimately impacts on the successful performance of the business.

2.4 Measuring Successful Business Performance

Measuring success in business performance, includes the satisfaction of all stakeholders. It should reflect in the financial results and how efficient the business performs operationally. According to Kaplan (2009) the balanced scorecards is an approach that firms can use to assess how healthy they are, and it is determined by incorporating financial and non-financial metrics. Varadarajan and Ramanujam (1990) explained that business performance includes both financial performances, shown by profitability and growth in sales growth, and operational performance which is reflected by increase in market share and value added. Zarzycka and Krasodomska (2022) agreed with the definition, stating that financial performance measures profitability while non-financial measures include growth in market share, customer satisfaction and growth in employee work force. Lebens and Euske (2006), on the other hand, summarised business performance as the ability of getting information to achieve financial and non-financial goals and the generation of certain actions by the firm to determine future results.

Waita (2014), described successful business performance as overall growth in sales, number of customers and profit while Behn (2003) mentioned that there are no generally accepted criteria for measuring performance. Performance should therefore be determined individually by firms in their ability to meet set goals and objectives and evaluated by measuring how firms are able to attain these goals.

In summary, successful business performance refers to the different methods which firms use resources that are available to them in achieving profits and set objectives. This can be explained in detail with the Performance Pyramid model, which was proposed by Cross and Lynch in 1992. This model has four objectives affecting both the internal and external effectiveness of the firm. The corporate vision of the organisation is determined, breaking down goals into long term, medium term, short term and thereafter daily plans and performance measures are set (Tangen, 2004). A firm will know that their performance is successful when sustainable profit is being made, employment is being generated and there are contributions from the firm to the development of the nation. Every organisation should therefore set goals in such a way that periodic evaluation can be carried out to ascertain if performance is below expectation such that amendments can be made on time to avoid business collapse.

3.0 Conclusion

This study highlights the role of entrepreneurial behaviours and competences for successful internationalisation. The results from the study show that behaviours and competences that improve entrepreneurial internationalisation include networking, adaptability, creativity, problem-solving innovation, strategic leadership abilities, risk taking and resilience. These enable the entrepreneurs to develop the capacity to overcome inevitable challenges that are

evident in international markets such as changing regulations, logistics and general fluctuations in the market.

This research shows how necessary it is for stakeholders and policy makers to develop enabling environment for improvement in behaviours and competences which can be achieved through trainings and workshops, supportive policies, access to funds and technology and infrastructure from the government etc. which will further empower them to operate effectively, grow and succeed. It is also clear from the study that entrepreneurs who improve on these behaviours and competences will be in a better position to take advantage of opportunities as they come up and maintain sustainable business growth. As economies begin to diversify through internationalisation, it is critical for the behaviours and competences to be identified and nurtured. It is important for SMEs to encourage continuous learning, creativity and innovation in their firms to increase their resilience against regular challenges.

Future studies on entrepreneurial internationalisation could examine artificial intelligence, digital technology and transformation as competences for successful entrepreneurial internationalisation.

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